

Thermodynamic Molar Properties of Aqueous Solutions of Copper Salts using Sound Velocity Measurements

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The partial molar volumes and compressibilities of Cu (m) benzene disulphonate, Cu acetate, Cu perchlorate, Cu nitrate and CuSO₄ are calculated from densities and sound velocity measurements at 25°. The investigated concentration range is between 0.01 and 1 molar.

The partial molar volume at infinite dilution was found to decrease in the following order ; Cu(m)BDS > Cu(OAc)₂ > Cu(ClO₄)₂ > Cu(NO₃)₂ > CuSO₄. However, the apparent molar compressibilities at infinite dilution were found to follow the following trend ; CuSO₄ > Cu(m) BDS > Cu(ClO₄)₂ > Cu(NO₃)₂ > Cu(OAc)₂.

In a previous communication¹, we examined the partial molar volumes and compressibilities from precise measurements of sound velocity and density of various calcium and magnesium salts. Some of these electrolytes have certain importance to Oceanography and help in predicting the properties of sea water.

In this communication we deal with various copper salts, like Cu(NO₃)₂, Cu(ClO₄)₂ and Cu-m-benzene disulphonate (Cu m - BDS) as completely dissociated salts^{2,3}. Copper acetate and Copper sulphate, as partially dissociated salt^{4,6}. Recently⁷ some work has been published concerning the effect of ionic association on the partial molar properties.

Experimental

Chemicals : All chemicals used in this study are reagent grades and recrystallized twice from deionized distilled water. Copper m-BDS, however, was synthesized⁸.

The exact concentrations of the stock solutions were determined by the EDTA titration and ion-exchange techniques. Further dilutions were made

just before running the experiments for both density and sound velocity measurements.

Apparatus and Measurements : Experimental details are given in a previous paper¹.

Results and Discussion

The partial molar volumes (ϕ_v 's) and molar compressibilities (ϕ_{κ_s} 's) have been determined in the same way as described in the previous paper. The results are given in Tables 1-5. Plotting ϕ_v against \sqrt{C} yielded straight lines which were extrapolated to zero concentrations to give the partial molar volumes at infinite dilution, ϕ_v° . This of course should only be dependent on the ion-solvent interactions rather than ion-ion interactions. One would expect to observe a decrease in ϕ_v° value as the molecular weight of the anion connected to the copper decreased. This is indeed the observed case except for the acetate. ϕ_v° was found to have the following trend. Cu m-BDS > Cu acetate > Cu perchlorate > Cu nitrate > Cu sulphate. Table 6 lists their ϕ_v° values at 25° and atmospheric pressure. It is interesting to notice that the electrolyte with the

TABLE 1—DENSITIES AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF Cu(m) BDS SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration Mole/L	Density(d) g-cm ⁻³	Apparent Molar volume \bar{v} (ml mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _a) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent Molar compressibility K _s (cm ³ -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ $\times 10^4$)
0.04	1.0053	94.26	1.4999	4.4261	- 83.81
0.06	1.0093	96.51	1.5000	4.3988	- 88.34
0.08	1.0130	100.78	1.5025	4.3725	- 88.77
0.10	1.0173	97.72	1.5046	4.3423	- 96.52
0.15	1.0273	98.49	1.5088	4.2760	- 98.98
0.20	1.0373	98.87	1.5133	4.2098	- 101.45
0.25	1.0471	99.91	1.5177	4.1461	- 103.23
0.30	1.0571	100.01	1.5221	4.0827	- 104.96
0.35	1.0668	101.80	1.5267	4.0217	- 106.09
0.40	1.0768	100.71	1.5317	3.9585	- 108.53
0.482	1.0832	100.65	1.5345	3.935	- 105.07

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TABLE 2—DENSITIES AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF Cu ACETATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration Mole/L	Density(d) g-cm ⁻³	Apparent Molar volume v (ml mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec × 10 ⁻³	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ × 10 ¹¹	Adiabatic apparent Molar compressibility K _s (cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴)
0.01	0.9982	68.85	1.4973	4.4686	-42.04
0.02	0.9994	65.34	1.4980	4.4591	-52.90
0.04	1.0017	66.09	1.4992	4.4416	-56.39
0.06	1.0036	73.08	1.5004	4.4232	-56.18
0.08	1.0059	71.48	1.5021	4.4056	-57.47
0.10	1.0082	70.56	1.5037	4.3886	-57.63
0.15	1.0134	73.003	1.5059	4.3510	-53.64
0.20	1.0187	73.52	1.5083	4.3148	-52.05
0.25	1.0238	74.95	1.5106	4.2802	-50.18
0.30	1.0289	75.77	1.5128	4.2468	-48.85

TABLE 3—DENSITIES AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF Cu(ClO₄)₂ AT 25°

Concentration Mole/L	Density(d) g-cm ⁻³	Apparent Molar volume v (ml mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec × 10 ⁻³	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ × 10 ¹¹	Adiabatic apparent Molar compressibility K _s (cm ² -mole ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴)
0.005	0.9981	56.71	1.4956	4.4792	-
0.01	0.9991	59.72	1.4957	4.4740	-
0.03	1.0031	61.72	1.4961	4.4540	-44.43
0.05	1.0070	64.13	1.4962	4.4361	-52.28
0.10	1.0169	64.03	1.4963	4.3921	-59.16
0.20	1.0368	64.08	1.4972	4.3027	-66.62
0.30	1.0566	64.40	1.4992	4.2110	-72.76
0.50	1.0959	65.07	1.5046	4.0907	-96.34
0.60	1.1152	65.85	1.5083	3.9416	-84.59
0.70	1.1345	66.41	1.5126	3.8526	-87.93
0.80	1.1541	66.45	1.5174	3.7010	-100.77
0.90	1.1734	66.82	1.5224	3.6770	-94.42
1.0	1.1947	65.11	1.5284	3.5832	-99.21

TABLE 4—DENSITIES AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF Cu(NO₃)₂ SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration Mole/L	Density (d) g-cm ⁻³	Apparent Molar volume v(ml mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec × 10 ⁻³	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ × 10 ¹¹	Adiabatic apparent Molar compressibility K _s (cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴)
0.01	0.9987	25.90	1.4961	4.4734	-
0.03	1.0017	34.27	1.4970	4.4547	-
0.05	1.0049	32.01	1.4975	4.4575	-63.19
0.10	1.0126	33.51	1.4995	4.3923	-71.77
0.20	1.0279	34.46	1.5035	4.3047	-75.99
0.30	1.0430	35.57	1.5075	4.2190	-78.27
0.40	1.0580	36.16	1.5118	4.1353	-80.07
0.50	1.0732	36.30	1.5164	4.0521	-82.17
0.60	1.0879	37.41	1.5210	3.973	-83.17
0.70	1.1029	37.41	1.5259	3.8942	-89.77
0.80	1.1180	37.44	1.5308	3.817	-86.11
0.90	1.1327	37.90	1.536	3.742	-87.13
1.0	1.1474	38.04	1.6410	3.670	-88.01

TABLE 5—DENSITIES AND APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF CuSO₄ SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration Mole/L	Density (d) g-cm ⁻³	Apparent Molar volume v(ml mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec × 10 ⁻³	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ × 10 ¹¹	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility K _s (cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴)
0.01	0.9987	2.363	1.4967	4.4698	-
0.02	1.0004	-5.85	1.4976	4.4569	-96.31
0.04	1.0039	-7.59	1.4992	4.4336	-109.50
0.06	1.0064	4.20	1.5003	4.4144	-101.40
0.08	1.0104	-5.9	1.5019	4.3878	-115.59
0.10	1.0138	-6.65	1.5033	4.3647	-116.99
0.15	1.0219	-4.89	1.5066	4.3112	-116.51
0.20	1.0302	-5.01	1.5098	4.2584	-116.84
0.25	1.0382	-3.88	1.5136	4.2099	-115.34
0.30	1.0465	-4.03	1.5164	4.1555	-117.18
0.366	1.0568	-2.56	1.5205	4.0926	-116.01

highest association has the least value for ϕ_v° . However, this kind of comparison may not be very fair since CuSO_4 is a 2 : 2 salt compared to the others which are 2 : 1 salts.

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC APPARENT MOLAR PARAMETER FOR THE FIVE COPPER SALTS

Electrolyte	ϕ_v° cm ³ - mole ⁻¹	F m sec ⁻¹ lit mol ⁻¹	$10^4 \times \phi_{K_s}^\circ$ cm ³ - mol ⁻¹ bar ⁻¹
Cu(m) BDS	95	91	-103.9
Cu(OAc) ₂	67.4	52	-52.29
Cu(ClO ₄) ₂	62.4	42.6	-87.41
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	32.0	43.3	-81.42
CuSO ₄	-9.8	65.0	-119.31

The adiabatic apparent molar compressibilities at infinite dilution, $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$, were calculated using methods as explained in the previous paper. The calculated values of F, ϕ_v° and $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ are tabulated in Table 6. It is worth noting that both the two methods should yield the same $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ values for the same electrolyte under the same conditions. However, many authors have found that this is not always the case. One notices that the second method, known as the extrapolation procedure, gives $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ values lower than the first one. This can be best explained by the reported data on tetraalkyl ammonium bromides and several 1 : 1 salts⁸⁻¹⁰.

We report here also that in the concentration range under investigation for the 2 : 1 and 2 : 2 copper salts that $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ using the extrapolation method

gave different values from those obtained by the first method.

This may be due to the error incurred by empirical extrapolation of $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ data obtained at concentrations for which the limiting law is not applicable. It is also worth noting that the two methods converged very nicely to the same $\phi_{K_s}^\circ$ values for the Ca and Mg salts of 2 : 1 and 2 : 2 types as shown in the previous paper.

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